

METHODS OF FORMING STUDENTS' CREATIVE-CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS

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Annotation. *The modern world requires individuals with a wide range of skills, including cognition, the application of many modes of thought, research, problem-solving ability, critical thinking abilities, and creativity. Learning styles are another important aspect, along with critical thinking, that play a crucial part in the process of issue solving. This study aimed to determine the importance and the ways of teaching and learning styles and critical thinking of students in their academic performance.*

Keywords: *critical thinking, internet, technology, education, foreign languages, games, AI.*

МЕТОДЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ У УЧАЩИХСЯ НАВЫКОВ ТВОРЧЕСКОГО КРИТИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ

Аннотация: *Современный мир требует людей с широким спектром навыков, включая познание, применение многих способов мышления, исследования, способность решать проблемы, способности критического мышления и творчество. Стили обучения — еще один важный аспект, наряду с критическим мышлением, который играет решающую роль в процессе решения проблем. Это исследование было направлено на определение важности и способов преподавания, стилей обучения и критического мышления студентов в их академической успеваемости.*

Ключевые слова: *критическое мышление, интернет, технологии, образование, иностранные языки, игры, ИИ.*

INTRODUCTION

As globalization is being faced by almost every single person on this planet, one has to have not only the needed knowledge but also know how to think critically to possess one's place in this competitive world. And it means, in today's rapidly changing and advanced information and communication technologies, educating the young generation as a highly spiritual and intellectually developed person is one of the priority directions of state education policy. Living in a society based on market relations requires everyone to have a wide range of knowledge. In this case, knowing a foreign language is especially important. Today students are to learn how to think critically and, in this case, they use a variety of learning methods during the learning process, relying on distinct variations in how they receive, process, and apply the knowledge they are learning. The teacher and educational and upbringing concerns are resolved during the learning process through student cooperation in class, independent work, and extracurricular activities.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Therefore, it is necessary to teach the young generation creative observation in the family and in educational institutions. For this, first of all, the idea of expanding and deepening the content of education and its content, in particular, including not only knowledge, skills, and qualifications but also the experience of creative activities that make up universal human culture—the culture of attitude toward the environment—should be on the agenda of the educational institutions. In general education schools, it is important to increase students' interest in science in the educational process, to ensure their independence and activity, and to form a cognitive process aimed at forming critical thinking. And this cannot be established without the help of learning the world,

and the world is taught and learned by teaching and learning languages. The development of independent creative thinking encourages the student to search during the learning process. This shows the most important aspects of the student's thinking activity. In this process, the student is actively searching with the teacher. The teacher possesses a crucial role in showing students how to think critically using various methods. When studying the level of creative and critical thinking of schoolchildren, it is important to observe their communication processes through their abilities to communicate in other languages rather than their own mother tongue.

RESULTS

Foreign languages, namely English, and educational games are of great importance in the development of creative and critical thinking in high school students. In this process, the teacher's ability to use English and educational games has a positive effect on the development of students' creative and critical thinking. In the educational process, creative role-playing games are not only a way to stimulate the learning of knowledge materials, but they also have great heuristic and persuasive power. Games allow you to perceive phenomena that appear as a single whole. And one can obtain different games with the aid of English, which is considered to be one of the most important educational languages that helps teachers not only as language teachers but as educators of any subject throughout the world. On this basis, it allows us to compare, differentiate, and perceive the studied phenomena as a whole. Various enterprises and nature travel games have a special pedagogical value in expanding students' imaginations and creative activities. Such games are played with the help of the internet, books, maps, and various documents. Such games rely on the imagination of students. All actions and experiences are defined by in-game roles. Pupils write diaries, letters, and collect various materials of a cognitive nature. The active presentation of material in these written documents accelerates their thinking processes. The specific aspects of these games are determined by the activation of students' perceptions and the creation of a unique form of activity—the creation of an atmosphere of friendship and cooperation between them. Such games expand the practical activities of students' imaginations. Such activity is carried out with the help of external actions. Therefore, it becomes a direct, continuous action. Accordingly, as a result of the game, students' imagination becomes a creative activity. As a result, they make a project of a certain thing and implement it with the help of external actions. As a result, cooperative play, work, and study activities are carried out among students. In this process, students work hard, analyze books, consult reference books, and study maps related to the topic. It is known that every person has a certain creative power. The basis of this creative power is the creation of new things. Students' imaginations will be creative and critical. In the process of reading educational or fiction literature, students are required to relive the reality described in these books in their memories. The teacher pays attention to the content and quality of the lessons in order to increase the interest of the students. For this, he tries to make children think and activate them. Guides the student to discussion in order to make him an active participant in the learning process in the classroom rather than a ready receiver of knowledge. Problem-based teaching methods provide effective results in shaping students' creative and critical thinking. One of the teaching methods that increases student activity in the learning process is the "working in small groups" method. Students work in small groups, and in this process, each group is given the opportunity to learn from each other, to evaluate what they have learned within their own potential, to value knowledge in different situations, and to draw conclusions. In addition, it teaches students to solve problems through cooperation.

DISCUSSION

It is necessary to work in the following order to develop students' critical thinking:

1. Problem-solving tasks and questions are put before the group of students, and they are asked questions that encourage them to think: Questions like: What do you think? How do you think it should be?
2. Students are given a certain amount of time to think among themselves.
3. Why do you think that students are allowed to express their opinions and to check their validity? Why did you come to this conclusion? You can ask questions like these.
4. Questions are asked about the opinions of other students in the group and about who does not approve of the opinions expressed.
5. Together with the students, the teacher discusses the opinions expressed by the groups and summarizes the opinions.
6. Pupils' reactions to accepted, generalized opinions are studied, and opinions are listened to.
7. Give and ask for feedback from each student about their own answers and their peers answers.

CONCLUSIONS

It is important for the teacher to be able to choose the methods and methods that serve to form the creative and critical thoughts of students and use them in the educational process, taking into account the age characteristics of students in the development of creative activity in students. Because the teaching methods used skillfully by the pedagogue in the course of the lesson serve to form the creative and critical thinking of the students.

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